

SURVEILLANCE CARD_Lyme borreliosis_ticks risk regions_surveillance card

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk regions where the vector is endemic (tick dragging or flagging) testing for <i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i> s.l..
2	Surveillance aim	Detection of a change of the geographic distribution/spread to new areas; possibly early detection of an increase in incidence, i.e., early epidemic detection.
3	Target species and group	Hard ticks – Genus <i>Ixodes</i> ; species <i>I. ricinus</i> and <i>I. persulcatus</i> .
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable.
5	Geographical area covered	Areas with high-risk of disease prevalence; areas where LB has been previously diagnosed; areas with recent tick vector expansion; preferred habitats of hard ticks: shady and humid woodlands, trails (1), clearings with grass, open fields and bushes, urban and rural areas.
6	Age group	Larvae, nymphs and adults.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Flagging a cloth in suitable vector habitat to collect questing ticks. (1)
8	Sampling time period	Ticks, are seasonally active and more likely to be detected from March to November, considering the period of maximum incidence of the disease in humans (2). However, the active period tick vector varies depending on the latitude, altitude and the actual temperature. (3)
9	Sampling matrix	Whole ticks.
10	Type of disease indicators	Presence of the pathogen (identification of <i>Borrelia</i> spirochetes) or DNA.
11	Sampling unit	Single ticks, testing at least 100 individuals per sampling location [VectorNet, 2022]
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Not applicable

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Tick species identification with subsequent detection of the pathogen by polymerase chain reaction (PCR), dark-field immunofluorescence microscopy, or bacterial culture. (4)
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component can contribute to identification of introduction of <i>Borrelia</i> in new areas, with high expected sensitivity [VectorNet, 2022]. However, results cannot be used directly for estimation of detection sensitivity or confidence of freedom since this is a biased (non-representative) sample of an unknown population.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Tick-borne encephalitis virus, <i>Anaplasma phagocytophilum</i> causing human granulocytic ehrlichiosis, <i>Francisella tularensis</i> causing Tularaemia, <i>Rickettsia helvetica</i> and <i>Rickettsia monacensis</i> , <i>Babesia divergens</i> and <i>Babesia microti</i> responsible for Babesiosis, Louping ill virus. (5)
18	References	<p>1) Salomon J, Hamer SA, Swei A. A Beginner's Guide to Collecting Questing Hard Ticks (Acari: Ixodidae): A Standardized Tick Dragging Protocol. J Insect Sci. 2020 Nov 1;20(6):11. doi: 10.1093/jisesa/ieaa073. PMID: 33135760; PMCID: PMC7604844.</p> <p>2) Petrulionienė A, Radzišauskienė D, Ambrozaitis A, Čaplinskas S, Paulauskas A, Venalis A. Epidemiology of Lyme Disease in a Highly Endemic European Zone. Medicina (Kaunas). 2020 Mar 5;56(3):115. doi: 10.3390/medicina56030115. PMID: 32151097; PMCID: PMC7143858.</p> <p>3) TECHNICAL REPORT Field sampling methods for mosquitoes, sandflies, biting midges and ticks VectorNet project 2014–2018</p> <p>4) WOA Health Technical disease card - <i>Borrelia</i> spp. (Infection with) Aetiology Epidemiology Diagnosis Prevention and Control Potential Impacts of Disease Agent Beyond Clinical Illness References, 2020</p>

		5) ECDC Ixodes ricinus - Factsheet for experts, last updated 31 Jul 2014
19	Additional comments	Information available about prevalence: 5 – 20 % [VectorNet, 2022]